

Insect resistance

Indian biotypes of the brown planthopper

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The existence of brown planthopper (BPH) biotypes complicates control of the insect by resistant varieties. BPH biotypes, based on differential reactions of rice varieties to BPH injury, have been established. Some entries are resistant to biotype 1 (common in the Philippines), but are killed by biotype 2. Similarly cultivars resistant to biotype 2, found in

the Philippines, Indonesia, Thailand, Vietnam, Taiwan, Korea, and Japan, are destroyed by biotype 3, which is not yet abundant in nature. Another biotype found in southern India and Sri Lanka damages varieties that are resistant to biotypes 1, 2, and 3.

Glasshouse screening of rice varieties against the BPH populations found in Hyderabad (southern India) and Pantnagar (northern India) was initiated at Pantnagar in 1974. Results clearly indicate the existence of an additional biotype (the Pantnagar population) that differs from the four mentioned above. When exposed to this biotype, varieties that are

resistant to the biotype in southern India and Sri Lanka and those resistant to the three other biotypes at IRRI succumb (see table). New genes for resistance to this biotype must be found; this biotype destroys all varieties with known resistance genes. ■

Reactions^a to brown planthopper biotypes of rice varieties with genes for resistance to given biotypes.

Variety	Reactions				
	Biotype 1 (IRRI)	Biotype 2 (IRRI)	Biotype 3 (IRRI)	Biotype 4 (Hyderabad)	Biotype 5 (Pantnagar)
<i>Bph 1 gene for resistance</i>					
Mudgo	R	S	R	S	S
Andaragahawewa	R	S	R	S	S
Dalwa Sanam (MTU15)	R	MR	R	S	S
IR26	R	S	R	S	S
RP9-6	MR	S	R	S	S
<i>bph 2 gene for resistance</i>					
ASD7	R	R	S	S	S
CR94-13	R	R	S	S	S
H5	R	MR	S	S	S
Murungkanyani 3	R	MR	S	S	S
Palasithari 60 1	R	R	S	S	S
Murungakayan 101 B	R	R	S	S	S
Murungakayan 303 B	R	MR	S	S	S
C62-1-2 30	R	R	S	S	S
<i>Bph 3 gene for resistance</i>					
Rathu Heenathi	R	R	R	R	S
Muthumanikan	R	R	R	S	S
PTB 19	R	R	R	R	S
Kuruhondarwala	R	R	R	MR	S
<i>bph 4 gene for resistance</i>					
Babawee	R	R	R	R	S
Lekamsamba	R	R	R	R	S
Gulai	R	R	R	R	S
<i>Unknown gene for resistance</i>					
PTB33	R	R	R	R	S
ARC6650	R	R	S	R	S

^aBased on Standard Evaluation System for rice scale: R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible.

Unusual occurrence of rice hispa on rice in Himachal Pradesh, India

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An epidemic of rice hispa *Diuraphis armigera*, once a minor rice pest in the Kangra Valley, occurred in 1979. Negligible rains with high ambient temperature and high relative humidity during the paddy seasons contributed significantly to the pest's abundance.

The epidemic was first noticed in early August 1979 at Nagrota, Baijnath, and Palampur. Almost all the varieties grown in the field, particularly the highly susceptible varieties HPU 71, HPU 734, HPU 741, T23 (local Basmati), China 988, and HPU 2004, were severely infested. Moderately infested were HPU 731, HPU 8021, RT42 (Himdhan), Norin 18, and IR579. In a field trial, a spray of permethrin (synthetic pyrethroid as Ambush 25 EC) at 0.025%, quinalphos or endosulfan or methylparathion at 0.05% controlled the rice hispa more effectively than BHC did. ■

An alternate biotype of green leafhopper in Bangladesh

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The presence in Bangladesh of a different biotype of green leafhopper (GLH) was suspected in 1967 when field plantings of IR8, which is resistant to GLH in the Philippines, were heavily infested. No apparent differences in morphology of

the insects from the two countries were recorded and insects collected in Bangladesh were confirmed to be *Nephotettix virescens*.

A germplasm collection of 2,361 strains, including 473 that are resistant to GLH at IRRI, was evaluated for GLH resistance at the Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Joydebpur, using techniques developed at IRRI. Varieties that possessed the single resistance genes *Glh 1*, *Glh 2*, *Glh 3*, *glh 4*, and *Glh 5* were included as differentials for detecting new biotypes. Varieties identified as resistant at BRRI were retested at IRRI.

Only 10 of the 473 rice varieties that were resistant to *N. virescens* at IRRI were also resistant at BRRI. The varieties Pankhari 203, ASD7, IR8, and ASD8, which carry the single dominant genes *Glh 1*, *Glh 2*, *Glh 3*, and *Glh 5*, respectively, at IRRI were susceptible at BRRI. PTB8, which carries the recessive resistance gene *glh 4*, was moderately resistant at BRRI, but several varieties that were resistant at BRRI reacted as susceptible at IRRI (see table). Such differences in varietal reactions indicate distinctly different biotypes in the

Differential reactions of some rice varieties to the local populations of green leafhopper at the Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI) and at the International Rice Research Institute (IRRI).

Variety	Reaction to green leafhopper at ^a		Nature of and gene for resistance
	BRRI	IRRI	
Pankhari 203	S	R	Monogenic, dominant, Glh1
ASD7	S	R	Monogenic, dominant, Glh2
Godalki	S	R	Monogenic, dominant, Glh2
Palasithari 601	S	R	Monogenic, dominant, Glh2
IR8	S	R	Monogenic, dominant, Glh3
Betong	S	R	Monogenic, dominant, Glh3
H5	S	R	Monogenic, dominant, Glh3
PTB8	MR	R	Monogenic, recessive, glh4
ASD8	S	R	Monogenic, dominant, Glh5
Kosatawee	MR	S	Monogenic, recessive, ?
DV 1 39	S	R	? ? ?
Sudu Madael	MR	S	? ? ?
Kiri Murunga	MR	S	? ? ?
Murungakayan 307	MR	S	? ? ?
TAPL 196	MR	R	Monogenic, dominant, Glh6
PTB18	R	R	Digenic, dominant, Glh1+6
Maddai Karuppan	R	MR	Monogenic, dominant, Glh7

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible.

populations of *N. virescens* in Bangladesh and at IRRI.

Results on the inheritance of GLH resistance in PTB18 are further evidence of biotype variation. PTB18 possesses two genes for GLH resistance at IRRI, one of which is allelic to *Glh 1*. In this study, a single dominant gene in PTB18,

which is allelic to *Glh 1*, conveyed green leafhopper resistance at BRRI.

No standard procedure for naming biotypes in insects is available. Therefore, for the present the GLH populations of Bangladesh and of the Philippines are being designated *Bangladesh biotype* (Bb), and *Philippine biotype* (Pb). ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Adverse soils tolerance

Boron toxicity in rice soils

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Although boron toxicity is widely considered a hazard in soils irrigated with high-boron water, literature references to field cases of boron toxicity in rice on such soils could not be found. But now we have evidence for such toxicity.

Boron toxicity is characterized by yellowing of the leaf tips, followed by the appearance of dark-brown elliptical blotches along the leaf edges, which later turn brown and die. Vegetative growth is not seriously depressed unless the toxicity is severe.

Those symptoms were observed on about 7 ha of an 80-ha farm located on soils (mainly Tropaquepts) derived from volcanic ash. The soils had been irrigated for 15 years with deep-well water with a boron content of 3.0–5.3 ppm.

The soils had pH values of 6.6 to 7.8, electrical conductivities (EC) (1 : 1) of 1.2–4.2 mmho/cm, and an available boron content of 3 to 11 ppm. The corresponding soil analyses for an unirrigated block were pH 5.6, EC 0.03 mmho/cm, and 1.2 ppm available boron, indicating that irrigation had increased alkalinity, salinity, and the boron content of the soils.

The shoot of the affected plants contained 32 to 39 ppm boron at flowering. IR40 showed more tolerance

for boron toxicity than IR8.

Boron toxicity may be an unrecognized factor limiting rice yields on soils irrigated with high-boron water (as is often the case in arid regions) and on soils subject to inundation by seawater (which is high in boron). ■

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